

PROPOSAL OF A COMPANY BIM GUIDE IN ALIGNMENT WITH ISO 19650

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Abstract

BIM adoption and implementation have been escalating due to its benefits during the design, construction, and operation phase of the construction projects. Enhancing lifecycle data management, improving quality and saving time and costs are just some of the advantages of a BIM implementation.

The high volume of information that needs to be produced, coordinated and communicated during the facility lifecycle, highlights the importance of efficient information management. Increasing coverage of BIM technology and the need for structured data management has consequently led to the proliferation of BIM-focused publications. Government authorities, industry associations, communities of practice and academic institutions have been developing BIM-focused guidance documents to promote BIM understanding, facilitate information management and standardise BIM implementation. These publicly available BIM documents contain guidelines, protocols and requirements that are focused on BIM deliverables, processes and workflows to minimize the barriers for the implementation of BIM technology.

In spite of variety and multiplicity of these documents, there is still a need for a guideline document that is both descriptive and instructive with strategic, managerial, and technical level recommendations to create a framework for supporting companies in BIM projects. This is also the case for BIMMS - BIM Management Solutions, an international consultancy company based in Portugal, that is willing to evolve on the systematic approach to BIM on its projects. Therefore, this research in collaboration with BIMMS aims to standardise BIM application and achieve a customized workflow for management of information generated over the entire lifecycle a facility.

To propose an efficient and well-structured BIM guide, an extensive research of existing BIM guidance documents developed by different organisations and universities was conducted, and their commonalities and deficiencies were determined. The proposed BIM guide contains a set of guidelines, definitions, and procedures for successful BIM practice in the organisation. The first immediate outcome from the BIMMS BIM Guide is to assist individuals new to BIM to better understand the BIM fundamentals. Furthermore, this document will assist all actors in a project to be aware of the company BIM strategies and produce, release, and receive data in a consistent format to have better project outcomes.

The proposed BIM guide follows the latest ISO standards on information management, ISO 19650-1 and ISO 19650-2 that provide a common framework for collaboration and information management over the project lifecycle. Utilising common terminologies and approaches would assist the BIM Guide to be internationally credible and recognisable.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-SeyedehAidaMirniazmandan-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/74eSDmGGI4k>

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